

Structural, Magnetic and Transport Properties of $\text{La}_{0.7}\text{Sr}_{0.3}\text{MnO}_3$ -Graphene Nanocomposite

Karuna Kumari^{1*}, Ashutosh Kumar, Jayakumar Balakrishanan, Ajay D Thakur and SoumyaJyoti Ray

Department of Physics, Indian Institute of Technology Patna, Bihta-801103, India
Department of Physics, Indian Institute of Technology Palakkad, Kerala-678557, India

karuna.phys@gmail.com , 8235038261

Abstract

$\text{La}_{0.7}\text{Sr}_{0.3}\text{MnO}_3$ (LSMO) polycrystalline sample was prepared using standard solid-state route, pure phase formation was confirmed using x-ray diffraction (XRD) and further supported by Rietveld Refinement. Magnetic properties of LSMO and graphene powder mixed LSMO show enhancement in magnetization as well as Curie Temperature which shows that addition of graphene can also enhance ferromagnetic ordering in the same way as Sr substituted LaMnO_3 enhances the magnetic properties owing to presence of double exchange mechanism. Resistivity measurements of LSMO and graphene mixed sample shows high magnetoresistance below Curie temperature.

Keywords: Solid-state route, magnetic properties, X-ray diffraction, magnetoresistance

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